

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF PARLIAMENTS IN THE SYSTEM OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS IN WARTIME: THE ROLE OF THE RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR

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Abstract

The full-scale aggression of the Russian Federation dictates the need to use all resources against the enemy. Here, the diplomatic front needs to be recognised no less than the military one, including international assistance, sanctions against aggressive states and military aid to Ukraine. This also means special attention to international parliamentary institutions in all areas of diplomatic activity. These institutions can be recognised as international parliamentarism and can be an important additional front in a country's international diplomacy. Thus, establishing relations with international parliamentary institutions provides Ukraine with broad and multidimensional opportunities for representation, which makes the issue of international parliamentarism particularly important for modern political science. The most important analysis concerns the main characteristics of international parliamentarism as an object of international relations that influence the formation of the international position of the world community. Of particular interest in this regard are the studies of international parliamentarism by representatives of Western political thought, which can become an important source for the formation of modern ideas about the nature of trends in the influence and involvement of international parliamentary institutions in the system of international relations.

The aim of this paper is to analyse theoretical data on parliamentarism and inter-parliamentary cooperation, as well as the impact of the Russian-Ukrainian war on foreign parliaments' assistance to Ukraine.

Keywords: Ukraine, war, Parliament, parliamentary diplomacy, Russia.

ANALYSIS OF THE WORK OF THE UKRAINIAN PARLIAMENT

The defence of Ukraine is the defence of constitutional democracy and the rule of law. However, the defence of Ukraine must take place within the framework of constitutional democracy and the rule of law. Of course, Ukraine's self-defence must be carried out with the use of force. However, the use of force and other measures to defend Ukraine must be carried out in a constitutional manner.

According to Article 75 of the Constitution of Ukraine, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine is the sole legislative body (see also Article 85(3)). In addition, the legislative power of the Assembly of Ukraine is preserved during martial law and a state of emergency. Indeed, the Verkhovna Rada plays an important role in such situations.

For example, pursuant to Article 83(3) of the Constitution of Ukraine, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine is obliged to convene a session within two days in the event of a state of emergency or martial law being declared by the President of Ukraine. Similarly, even if the President of Ukraine issues a decree declaring martial law or a state of emergency pursuant to Article 106(20) of the Constitution of Ukraine, the Verkhovna Rada must approve such decree within two days pursuant to Article 85(31) of the Constitution of Ukraine. If the Verkhovna Rada is not convened within the prescribed period and does not approve the Presidential Decree, the state of emergency or martial law will not be introduced [9].

It should be noted that of particular constitutional importance is the fact that the legislative powers of the

Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine are preserved during martial law and a state of emergency, i.e. the Constitution of Ukraine does not transfer legislative powers to the President in these cases. According to Ruslan Stefanchuk, Speaker of the Ukrainian Parliament [1]: "Since the beginning of Russia's invasion of Ukraine on 24 February 2022, the Verkhovna Rada has held seven plenary sessions, during which it adopted 13 resolutions and 88 laws. In addition, 18 bills are currently at the first reading stage".

In turn, to ensure the functioning of the democratic structure of government and the exercise of state power on the basis of the separation of powers, it is crucial that the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (Parliament) functions effectively and is further modernised in accordance with established European and international standards. In the context of the parliamentary reform, new challenges arise to improve the work of the Secretariat of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine and to train its staff in accordance with European standards and best practices of other countries. The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine and its Secretariat should be as open an institution as possible, whose activities are clearly regulated by the current legislation, determined by universal human values and ethical standards, and facilitate the recruitment of patriotic professionals. The Report and Roadmap for Strengthening the Institutional Capacity of the Secretariat of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine [6], some of whose recommendations are directly related to staff development.

The Resolution of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine of 17 March 2016, adopted on the basis of the recommendations of the European Parliament's mission, "On Measures to Implement Recommendations on Internal

Reform and Strengthening the Institutional Capacity of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine" [14], sets out the priority areas of internal reform and professional development of the Secretariat's staff.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE CONCEPTS OF "PARLIAMENTARISM" AND "INTER-PARLIAMENTARY COOPERATION"

From a theoretical point of view, it is important to define the general concept of the term "parliamentarism".

The concept of "parliamentarism" is used to describe a form of government organisation that is characterised by the leading position of the parliament in the system of supreme bodies of the state and the existence of a parliamentary method of government formation [11]. At the same time, the government in a parliamentary system influences the legislature through its right of legislative initiative, which is given priority; ministers have the right to demand to be heard during a parliamentary session; the government actively participates in the legislative process at all stages and has a significant impact on the procedure for passing and voting on draft laws [8].

We believe that special attention should be paid to the scientific work of M.Hrushevsky, who, as the leader of the Ukrainian People's Republic, had to implement constitutionalism and parliamentarism. According to his plan, as a result of the establishment of a democratic electoral system based on universal, equal, direct and secret ballot and aimed at ensuring the widest possible representation of all segments of the population, the overall structure of central and local government should be based on three levels of "autonomy and representation": the autonomy of communities, sub-districts (volosts) and elected authorities. Ukraine acts as an equal participant in international communication, actively contributes to the strengthening of peace and international security and is directly involved in European processes and European institutions" [4].

Constitutional definitions that define the parliament as the "supreme representative body" are conceptually unsuccessful (Georgia, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan). Such a definition implies the existence of a system of subordinate representative bodies, and the parliament can be considered the "crown" of this system. This definition of parliament is an anachronism and a kind of inversion of the organisation of state power based on the principle of collegiality. The constitutional definition of the parliament as "the supreme representative and legislative body" (Moldova, Tajikistan) is also not successful. In this case, there is a possibility of misunderstanding whether there are other, lower legislative bodies in the state. This approach also stems from the Soviet theories of state power, which recognised parliament as the body of state power. The idea of the parliament as the "supreme body of state power" is also unacceptable, as it is stated in Article 7 of the 1978 Constitution of the Ukrainian SSR.

It is worth noting that in some countries the term "representative of the people" has acquired an official meaning. For example, in the UK, the law on parliamentary elections is called the Representation of the

People Act. In political and academic texts, the parliament itself is often directly or indirectly referred to as the representative body of the people.

Let us consider the opinion of the prominent legal scholar B.O. Kistiakivskiy. The author believes that: "The most important function of the state is legislative activity. In a constitutional state, the government is fully subordinated to the representatives of the people" [5, p. 250].

There are several stages in the development of parliamentarism in Ukraine.

1. *At the macro level, it is about improving the entire political system and preparing all institutions for parliamentarism.*

2. *Complete the formation of the parliament and ensure full recognition of its institutions.*

3. *The formation of the parliament must be completed in order for society to realise the need for the parliament to function in the political system as the most important channel of influence on the behaviour of those in power, despite the shortcomings of parliamentarism, and for serious changes to take place in the subconscious and political and legal culture of the people.*

We support the opinion of A. Pogorelova, a researcher on Ukrainian parliamentarism, who believes that Ukraine needs a quality government, i.e. a strong and unified government. After all, the division of power into legislative, executive, and judicial is a purely functional, professional division. And the opinions imposed on society, discussions about which power is more important, are not only unproductive, but also inherently wrong [12].

Inter-parliamentary cooperation is a legitimate interaction that is actively pursued by the representative bodies of a country - the diplomatic service, the head of the executive branch, structural units or individual parliamentarians - in order to find mutually acceptable approaches and jointly address common (international) problems.

Inter-parliamentary cooperation is characterised by the following features:

1. Equality of participants;
2. Voluntariness;
3. International legal proactivity (carried out exclusively at the initiative of the parties);
4. Regulatory and legal orderliness (implementation on an international and domestic (national) basis);
5. Wide geography of country relations;
6. Focus on solving urgent problems of our time;
7. A variety of forms and methods of implementation [2].

The purpose of interparliamentary cooperation should also be defined. It is diverse and includes, in particular:

1. Improving mutual understanding between countries;
2. Democratisation of interstate relations;
3. To represent the interests of their people with dignity;
4. Increase the democratic legitimacy of international organisations;
5. Promoting global social and political stability;

6. Promoting a change from confrontation in international relations to a contractual basis for constructive dialogue to develop partnerships between countries and regions;

7. Promoting the solution of international problems of any level [2].

When the parliamentary system was first established, foreign policy measures and direct relations with foreign countries were the prerogative of the executive branch. However, over time, the role of parliament in international relations has gradually increased, and inter-parliamentary relations have become very important. Despite the existence of multidimensional and sometimes contradictory trends in the development of parliamentarism, by the end of the 19th century, inter-parliamentary cooperation became a practice of international relations. forms of interaction expressed in differentiated forms.

It should also be noted that the concepts of "parliament" and "parliamentarism" are close, but not synonymous. The parliament, as a legislative body, is called upon not only to represent the interests of the people, but also to ensure the effective functioning and interaction of the legislative, executive and judicial branches at the highest level of the state, which is a key feature of democracy. According to S. B. Havrysh, the existence of a clear delineation between different spheres of power, stable functioning and interaction achieved through the leading role of the country's representative body is a sign of the existence of parliamentarism in the state. "The existence of parliamentarism in a country depends on and is determined by the presence of a strong, constructive, effective and authoritative parliament. Parliament has its traditional prerogatives and fully exercises them in its practical activities. This ensures that the representative body of the country has a leading place in the state structure of governance" [3, p. 3].

In addition, according to the Constitution of Ukraine [10], Ukraine's international activities are aimed at ensuring its national interests and security by maintaining peaceful cooperation on terms of mutual benefit with all participants in the international community. The Constitution of Ukraine, specifically Article 85, defines the powers of the Verkhovna Rada in the field of foreign relations. These include: determining the principles of the state's foreign policy; hearing annual and extraordinary addresses of the President of Ukraine on the external situation of Ukraine; declaring a state of war and peace upon the President's proposal; approving the President's decision to use the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations in the event of armed aggression against Ukraine; approving decisions to provide military assistance to other states, to send units of the armed forces of other states to the territory of Ukraine; giving consent within the time limit established by law

We believe that the growing role of inter-parliamentary cooperation is an objective and natural consequence of global development, as parliamentarians shape international law, have the authority to express the will of states and facilitate the process of representing their national interests in the international arena.

The entry of parliamentarians into the sphere of international relations and international cooperation is the result of parliamentary diplomacy. In the modern world, parliamentary diplomacy is carried out alongside classical diplomacy in organisations such as the Council of Europe and the OSCE, which represent both the legislative and executive branches of government. Other reasons for the development of parliamentary diplomacy include the growing democratisation of the rule of law, the need for civilised lobbying of national interests, including corporate and regional ones, in the international arena, and the justification of using various resources for international cooperation to secure the political commitment of states to the international community.

In our opinion, inter-parliamentary cooperation is an important institution of representative democracies that contributes to solving many contemporary state and legal issues. Today, inter-parliamentary cooperation covers such areas as international terrorism, drug trafficking, organised crime, poverty alleviation, combating illegal immigration, promoting disarmament, energy, economy, environment and human security. The modern evolution of representative institutions is characterised by the increasing involvement of parliaments in decision-making at the national, regional and global levels: instead of influencing foreign policy decisions, the EU's inter-parliamentary cooperation institutions are part of a multi-level parliamentarism, i.e. a network of international parliamentary cooperation, within which national parliaments, by engaging in formal and informal communication at the international level, contribute to the creation of a system in which they are

The principle of interparliamentary cooperation is a fundamental and guiding concept that forms the basis for regulation and implementation. Given the sovereignty of the state and the legal supremacy of the constitution in any national legal system, the basis of inter-parliamentary cooperation is formed by the basic constitutional principles that form the foundation of the constitutional order of each country. Among them, the principles of democracy, rule of law, separation of powers, socio-political pluralism, unitary system, recognition of a person as the highest social value, recognition of international legal standards, etc. are of great importance for Ukraine.

The principles of inter-parliamentary cooperation can be formalised in the relevant international legal documents and national laws regulating such parliamentary activities (formulated in the form of separate principle provisions), or can logically follow from the content of the relevant legal documents and established inter-parliamentary practice.

COOPERATION BETWEEN THE PARLIAMENTS OF THE WORLD AND UKRAINE

In the modern world, numerous international treaties have been concluded to protect people both in peacetime and during armed conflicts. Unfortunately, this codification has not resulted in enhanced protection of people in times of war and does not adequately guar-

antee the protection of people's rights from the arbitrariness of authoritarian regimes. In 1945, the UN Charter prohibited war, but since then, more armed conflicts have started than ended, and more civilians have died.

It is worth noting that the outbreak of the full-scale Russian-Ukrainian war has shown millions of people around the world the essence of the Russian Federation and the consequences of its actions. The role of parliaments in the system of international relations in wartime is important.

The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine calls on parliaments and governments, international organisations to unite in the pursuit of building a just international order and restoring the territorial integrity of the Ukrainian state, to continue to provide political, military, financial, economic, energy, humanitarian and other assistance, to increase sanctions pressure on Russia, to recognise Russia as a state sponsor of terrorism and its actions as genocide of the Ukrainian people, and to support the Peace Formula proposed by President Volodymyr Zelenskyy [15].

Next, let us note Volodymyr Zelenskyy's Formula for Peace, which consists of the following points:

1. *Radiation and nuclear safety.*
2. *Food security.*
3. *Energy security.*
4. *Release of all prisoners and deportees.*
5. *Implementation of the UN Charter and restoration of the territorial integrity of Ukraine and the world order.*
6. *Withdrawal of Russian troops and cessation of hostilities.*
7. *Justice.*
8. *Ecocide, the need for immediate protection of nature.*
9. *Preventing escalation.*
10. *Fixing the end of the war [17].*

It is important to note that the implementation of each point of the Peace Formula depends on the international diplomacy of parliaments around the world. It is the parliaments that decide to make important decisions to help Ukraine.

There is no doubt that Russia is attacking Ukraine's sovereignty, territorial integrity and political independence. However, its armed attack is also an attack on Ukraine's constitutional order. Ukraine is a constitutional democracy based on the rule of law. Russia is using military force to introduce unconstitutional changes in Ukraine outside the rules, institutions and procedures established by the Constitution of Ukraine. In addition, Russia is also attempting to introduce changes in Ukraine's foreign policy under armed pressure.

At the same time, the Ukrainian parliament calls on the world to use all means and opportunities, including the International Criminal Court, to bring to justice

those who have committed war crimes and crimes against humanity on the territory of Ukraine, as well as to bring to justice the military and political leadership of the Russian Federation found guilty of aggression by establishing a special international tribunal. At the same time, they stressed the need to develop mechanisms for using the frozen movable and immovable assets of Russian citizens abroad to compensate Ukraine for the damage caused.

Since 24 February 2022, most countries have been supporting Ukraine with both financial and military assistance. Currently, these are European countries and the United States. A special place among this support is occupied by the Lend-Lease Act, approved by the US Congress on 7 April this year. Signed on 9 May by Joe Biden, this document recalls a similar programme that operated during the Second World War [7].

It should be noted that the war in Ukraine has disrupted important global processes, increasing uncertainty and unpredictability, which has led to nervousness in the behaviour of players. It has become much more difficult to predict the future, set strategic and tactical priorities, and coordinate the ongoing interaction of states within a common framework to overcome the crisis.

The West is currently undergoing a process of collective strengthening and integration. Signs of this are the accession of Finland and Sweden to NATO and the change in European countries' approaches to collective and national security. This can be clearly seen in the case of Germany, the UK, Poland and other European countries, which intend to significantly strengthen their armed forces and enhance their military and political role in Europe. The growing political solidarity in the West is evidenced by the very rapid adoption of unprecedented sanctions against Russia and support programmes for Ukraine, as well as coordinated pressure on Russia in authoritative international bodies such as the UN Security Council, G20 and the Council of Europe.

Despite certain differences on issues such as "military" or "diplomatic" methods of conflict resolution, the scope and form of military and technical assistance to Ukraine, and attitudes towards Russia's post-war future, for more than six months Western groups have managed to find and maintain a degree of unity in response to Russian aggression.

Over the past year, Ukraine has improved its perception as an ally in the G-7 and BRICS countries more than any other country. This means that the governments of the most influential countries in the world, together with their parliaments, will be more likely to make important decisions to help Ukraine in this war [13].

Fig. 1. Attitudes of other countries' authorities towards Ukraine in 2021

Fig. 2. Attitudes of other countries' authorities towards Ukraine in 2022

While in November 2021, the number of countries that considered Ukraine an ally exceeded the number of those who considered it an enemy by 13.4%, in November 2022, it was already 35.5%. According to the report, Ukraine is considered an ally most of all in the UK, where the above figure increased from 13% to 64%. In the other G-7 countries, the figure ranges from 31% in Japan to 47% in Canada. Previously, the figure ranged from 8% in Germany to 17% in Canada and the United States [16].

According to the above, it appears that the Russian-Ukrainian war has helped to improve international relations between Ukraine and other countries. For example:

1. *The British parliament has shown considerable interest in the political situation in Ukraine, especially since the beginning of the Russian-Ukrainian "hybrid" war. In terms of aid to Ukraine, the UK is far ahead of any other country except the United States.*

2. *The European Parliament voted to provide Ukraine with €18 billion in macro-financial assistance in 2023.*

3. *The European Parliament strongly condemns the aggression of the Russian Federation and the invasion of Ukraine.*

We would like to draw attention to the fact that Russia, which once was a profitable economic partner and an integral part of the international security system, has become a malicious and dangerous actor that vio-

lates international law in all its aspects, a source of danger and an international terrorist, and relations with it have become dangerous and threaten its own reputation. At the same time, the fact that this entity possesses, on the one hand, resources vital for its existence and development, and, on the other hand, a powerful arsenal (nuclear weapons) capable of destroying all life, forces global actors to pursue a very balanced policy towards Russia.

We believe that the war has highlighted problems with the effectiveness of existing economic and security alliances. The main problems here are likely to be underestimation of risks, inability to prevent crises, slow response to crises, and irresponsibility of individual members in terms of resource requirements. In this context, the conclusions about the end of globalisation, the end of the era of large alliances and the transition of leadership to network structures in the form of autonomous regional and sub-regional unions, alliances and coalitions are telling.

Collective opposition to Russia is already one of the symbols of the new unity of countries. This has a direct impact on the strategy of defeating Russia (where a certain consensus has been formed in the camp of democracies, expressed in the documents of the EU, G7 and NATO summits), as well as on the duration of the war and the vision of the future of Ukraine and Russia.

Inter-parliamentary cooperation is an element of multi-vector foreign policy development related to the activities of inter-parliamentary institutions within the framework of special rules and procedures of interaction, namely

1. Democratisation of state relations.
2. Involvement of the parliament in general and its individual representatives in the development of the foreign policy agenda.
3. The growing importance of inter-parliamentary diplomacy, which is based on informal nature, as a tool for articulating the national interests of a modern state.

It follows from the above that not only the sovereignty of the country, but also the security of the whole of Europe depends on the actions of parliaments around the world, the speed of decision-making and the amount of support for Ukraine. Every month we can see an increase in assistance to Ukraine in all areas.

CONCLUSIONS

Modern globalisation has in various ways intensified the diplomatic activities of legislatures and promoted the development of parliamentary diplomacy and inter-parliamentary cooperation. The Ukrainian parliament has considerable experience in this area, and the study of inter-parliamentary cooperation is of great importance for Ukraine in its efforts towards European integration.

Russia is attacking Ukraine's sovereignty, territorial integrity and political independence. However, its armed attack is also an attack on Ukraine's constitutional order. Ukraine is a constitutional democracy based on the rule of law. Russia has used military force to impose unconstitutional changes in Ukraine outside the rules, institutions and procedures set out in the Ukrainian Constitution [14]. Moreover, under armed

pressure, Russia is trying to make changes to Ukraine's foreign policy. Defending Ukraine means defending constitutional democracy and the rule of law.

However, Ukraine's defence must be carried out within the framework of constitutional democracy and the rule of law. Of course, Ukraine's self-defence must be carried out with the use of force. However, the use of force and other measures to defend Ukraine must be carried out in accordance with the Constitution.

Inter-parliamentary cooperation is a legal interaction between the national representative bodies as bodies of external relations, their heads, structural units or individual parliamentarians, which is carried out on a proactive basis in order to find mutually acceptable approaches and jointly solve problems of common (international) interest.

In conclusion, democracy is an integral part of parliamentarism. Parliamentarism is a system of interaction between the state and society, characterised by the recognition of the primary or special and important role of national collective permanent representative institutions in the exercise of state power. It is the parliaments of other countries that decide whether to provide assistance to Ukraine in political, military, financial, economic, energy, humanitarian and other areas. They also determine sanctions, which are regularly adopted by many countries.

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